

UNITED4Surveillance pilot report (template)

1. Describe the aim and objectives of your pilot study

The National Institute of Public Health (Slo.: Nacionalni inštitut za javno zdravje - NIJZ) in collaboration with the University Medical Centre Ljubljana (Slo.: Univerzitetni klinični center Ljubljana - UKCL) conducted a pilot that will provide the basis for the future development of national electronic health records (EHR)-based surveillance of severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) in Slovenia that would replace the current “paper-based” national surveillance of SARI (named EPISARI).

NIJZ developed surveillance of SARI (EPISARI) within the comprehensive surveillance of COVID-19. By April 2021, the national EPISARI Network was established in collaboration with all Slovenian acute care hospitals. The objective was to monitor the national weekly numbers of SARI cases testing positive for SARS-CoV-2 admitted to hospitals and intensive care units (ICUs). In addition, we monitored the weekly numbers of all SARI cases (not only cases testing positive for SARS-CoV-2), SARI cases tested for SARS-CoV-2 infection, in-hospital deaths of SARI COVID-19 cases admissions, patients with COVID-19 as a secondary diagnosis at admission, COVID-19 cases diagnosed during hospitalisation (community-acquired or healthcare-associated). The aim was to contribute to evidence-based public health policies for prevention and control of COVID-19. These data were also used to estimate the vaccine effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccines against SARI COVID-19 hospitalizations.

In 2025, the legal basis for SARI surveillance changed. We no longer collect data on SARI cases COVID-19 as a secondary diagnosis at admission and SARI cases COVID-19 diagnosed during hospitalisation, but we started to collect data on SARI admissions to hospitals and ICUs together with data about the other pathogens of public health importance causing SARI (influenza and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV)) in addition to SARI cases COVID-19. The current legal basis for EPISARI is the article 13 of the “Act on additional intervention measures to ensure accessibility in healthcare”, which was adopted in December 2024. The text of the article 13 is as follows:

“(1) For the purpose of epidemiological monitoring of hospitalizations due to acute respiratory infections and acute respiratory infections in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or respiratory syncytial virus (hereinafter referred to as: RSV) was confirmed, hospitals shall submit to the National Institute of Public Health (hereinafter referred to as: NIJZ) on a weekly basis the number of persons admitted to hospitals due to acute respiratory infections and the EMŠO of the following persons:

- 1. persons admitted to hospital due to acute respiratory infection in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or RSV was confirmed,*
- 2. persons admitted to intensive care units due to acute respiratory infection in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or RSV was confirmed and*

3. *persons who died in hospital due to acute respiratory infection in which the cause of death was infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or influenza viruses or RSV.*

(2) The provisions of the Health Care Databases Act (Slo.: Zakon o zbirkah podatkov s področja zdravstvenega varstva (ZZPPZ) shall apply to the collection, processing and transmission of personal data referred to in the previous paragraph, their protection, recording, application of methodological principles and supervision, as they apply to the NIJZ 48 Communicable Diseases Database (CDD) from Annex 1 of the ZZPPZ. Under the same conditions, the collection shall also be linked to other collections managed in accordance with the ZZPPZ for the performance of tasks referred to in Article 23a of the Health Care Act (Slo.: Zakon o zdravstveni dejavnosti – ZZDej).

(3) The measure referred to in this Article shall be valid from 1 January 2025 to 31 December 2025. If the expert opinion of the NIJZ shows that acute respiratory infections and respiratory infections in which infection with the SARS-CoV-2 virus, influenza viruses or RSV has been confirmed are still occurring continuously, the Government may extend the measure referred to in this Article by decision no more than twice, each time for a maximum of six months. The decision to extend the measure shall be published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia.”

Our future EHR-based near real-time national SARI surveillance system will provide better and more timely surveillance data including data about the pathogens of public health importance causing SARI (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV).

The main objectives of planned EHR-based SARI surveillance are among patients of all Slovenian acute care hospitals, as well as in the general population of Slovenia, to monitor near real time:

- (a) the incidence of SARI admissions to hospitals (overall, by age groups, by different etiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV),
- (b) the incidence of SARI admissions to ICUs (overall, by age groups, by different etiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV),
- (c) in-hospital mortality due to SARI (overall, by age groups, by different etiology (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, RSV).

2. Describe the expected output prior to start of the pilot

Our expected outputs of the pilot were to prepare a draft of national EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol based on the experiences from the pilot in which we:

- identified the core data items needed and respective coding,
- mapped availability of relevant data for EHR-based SARI surveillance in the different information technology (IT) systems of the UKCL,
- prepared recommendations to improve and adjust such data availability in the UKCL IT systems,

- prepared proposals for respective information solutions in the UKCL IT systems,
- prepared proposals for EHR-based SARI surveillance data submission to the Central Register of Patients' Data (Slo.: Centralni register podatkov o pacientih - CRPP) at the NIJZ (The CRPP is a national system for recording and exchanging EHR at the national level, which includes patient summaries and various healthcare documents. The CRPP is managed and coordinated by NIJZ).

3. Briefly describe the method(s) used

Throughout the pilot, in collaboration with NIJZ and UKCL, we:

- reviewed available SARI surveillance literature,
- explored EHR-based surveillance of communicable diseases legal framework,
- explored availability of data and mapped data sources for EHR-based SARI surveillance in Slovenia,
- studied different lists of variables and coding systems and prepared drafts of different data models (lists of variables together with respective coding),
- discussed possible approaches to EHR-based SARI surveillance with different stakeholders such as the Ministry of Health, National Laboratory for Health, Environment and Food (Slo.: Nacionalni laboratorij za zdravje, okolje in hrano – NLZOH) and
- prepared a draft of the future Slovenian EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol.

4. Report the principal finding(s) of your pilot study

Based on our pilot results, we prepared the first draft of the Slovenian EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol with:

- objectives of our surveillance system,
- definitions for SARI cases admissions to hospitals and ICUs, SARI deaths and microbiological criteria for confirmation of infections with SARS-CoV-2, influenza viruses and RSV,
- data models (lists of variables with coding) for EHR-based SARI surveillance:
 - Data (variables) to be transferred to CRPP from hospitals,
 - Data (variables) to be transferred to CRPP from microbiology laboratories,
 - Data (variables) about deaths submitted to the CRPP by healthcare providers,
 - Data (variables) to be harvested from Central Register of Population (CRP),
 - Data (variables) harvested from CRPP into the CDD.

We also prepared an IT solution for accepting real time data generated at the patient admission to hospital and discharge from hospital in the CRPP. Respective IT solution to submit such data from one of the UKCL IT systems used by the Infectious Diseases Hospital to CRPP near real time was developed also and will be tested during the pilot follow-up period.

In addition, in 2024, we managed to negotiate with the Ministry of Health to provide the current legal basis for EPISARI which is described above.

During the pilot follow-up period, we will continue with our activities to digitalize of national SARI surveillance system which will reduce the workload for hospitals that currently send paper based weekly reports to NIJZ as well as the workload of Communicable Diseases Centre staff at the NIJZ.

5. Formulate your main take-away(s) and recommendations of your pilot study and provide rationale(s)

Our main take away of our pilot study is the first draft of our Slovenian EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol, which provides a basis for the future development of our national EHR-based SARI surveillance. The protocol contains our plan to develop national EHR-based SARI surveillance system within the EHR-based surveillance of all communicable diseases within the infrastructure of eHealth and CRPP, including data models with sets of variables with respective coding.

This first draft of the Slovenian EHR-based SARI surveillance protocol will be further updated according to future developments with respect to EHR-based surveillance of communicable diseases in general and changes of the Slovenian and European legal framework.

6. Reflect on most relevant limitations and/or challenges (including potential solutions) and the degree of achieving expected output of your pilot study

Our progress towards future EHR-based SARI surveillance during the pilot was substantial and we have the first draft of the protocol which provides a basis for the future development of our national EHR-based SARI surveillance in Slovenia.

In addition, there is a need to establish a legal framework for EHR-based surveillance of all communicable diseases, including SARI, and infections like SARS-CoV-2, influenza, and RSV infection as the current Slovenian legal basis for EPISARI will only last until the end of 2026. This legal framework should also permit data access and linkage across various sources and registries to meet our surveillance objectives. The upcoming Digitalization of Health Care Act, currently being prepared by the Ministry of Health and expected to pass through the Slovenian parliament in 2026 is set to address this issue.

The main limitation to implement our planned EHR-based SARI surveillance may be insufficient resources to develop all the proposed IT solutions (also due to the diversity of the various IT systems in the hospitals) to provide adequate data flow and generate of EHR-based SARI surveillance reports.

7. Did your pilot study contribute to strengthened (inter)national infectious disease surveillance? Why or why not?

Our pilot contributed to strengthening national infectious disease surveillance by paving the way for a more efficient, sustainable EHR-based near real-time surveillance system for SARI.

By replacing the current paper-based surveillance in the future, we aim to obtain more timely and accurate data on SARI cases, including information on key pathogens such as SARS-CoV-2, influenza, and RSV. This digitalization will not only improve and enhance the quality of surveillance but also reduce the reporting burden for hospitals and data management burden for NIJZ staff, ultimately improving the overall effectiveness of infectious disease surveillance at both nationally and potentially internationally.

UNITED4Surveillance legal/privacy barriers (template)

1. To what degree did you experience legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study?
- | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| No | Little | Some | Large | Very large |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

2. **If so, please provide a detailed example(s) on the experienced legal/privacy barrier(s) in your pilot study.**

Prior the pilot, the legal basis for collecting etiological data for SARI surveillance was limited to SARI patients, admitted to hospitals due to SARS-CoV-2 infection, with the legal basis expiring at the end of 2024.

3. **How did you cope with and/or solve the experienced legal and/or privacy barrier within your pilot study? If not, what is your suggestion to solve this legal/privacy barrier(s) in the future?**

We have overcome this barrier by successfully negotiating with the Ministry of Health to provide the current legal basis for EPISARI within the "Law on Additional Intervention Measures to Ensure Accessibility in Healthcare" that was adopted in December 2024. The respective article 13 is cited above. This legal basis will be in force until the end of 2026 and provided also for expanding the SARI surveillance system to SARI confirmed influenza and confirmed RSV infection cases in addition to COVID-19-related SARI cases.